

Visible Light Photoswitchable Covalent Tetra-*ortho*-fluoro-azobenzene Carbon Nanodot Hybrids for Optostimulation

Paul P. Debes,^[a,b] Dominic Schatz,^[a,c] Anthea Villano,^[d,e] Yagmur Aydogan-Sun,^[f] Juan Pablo Martínez,^[g] Michal Langer,^[h] Janis Hessling,^[i] Monika Schönhoff,^[i] Bernd M. Smarsly,^[a,b] Silvio Osella,^[g] Josef Wachtveitl,^[f] Maria Rosa Antognazza,^[c] Giuseppe M. Paternò,^[d] Teresa Gatti,^{*,[a,b,j]} Hermann A. Wegner^{*,[a,c]}

[a] Paul P. Debes, Dominic Schatz, Bernd M. Smarsly, Teresa Gatti, Hermann A. Wegner
Center for Materials Research
Justus Liebig University
Heinrich-Buff-Ring 16, 35392, Giessen (Germany)

[b] Paul P. Debes, Bernd M. Smarsly, Teresa Gatti
Institute of Physical Chemistry
Justus Liebig University
Heinrich-Buff-Ring 17, 35392, Giessen (Germany)

[c] Dominic Schatz, Hermann A. Wegner
Institute of Organic Chemistry
Justus Liebig University
Heinrich-Buff-Ring 17, 35392, Giessen (Germany)
E-mail: Hermann.A.Wegner@org.chemie.uni-giessen.de

[d] Anthea Villano, Giuseppe M. Paternò
Department of Physics
Politecnico di Milano
Piazza L.da Vinci 32, 20133 Milano (Italy)

[e] Anthea Villano, Maria Rosa Antognazza
Center for Nano Science and Technology
Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia
Via Rubattino 81, 20134 Milano (Italy)

[f] Yagmur Aydogan-Sun, Josef Wachtveitl
Institute of Physical and Theoretical Chemistry
Goethe University
Max von Laue-Strasse 7, 60438, Frankfurt (Germany)

[g] Juan Pablo Martínez, Silvio Osella
Chemical and Biological Systems Simulation Lab, Centre of New Technologies
University of Warsaw
2c Banacha Street, 02-097, Warszawa (Poland)

[h] Michal Langer
IT4Innovations
VSB – Technical University of Ostrava
17.listopadu 2172/15, 70800, Ostrava-Poruba (Czech Republic)

[i] Janis Hessling, Monika Schönhoff
Institute of Physical Chemistry
University of Münster
Corrensstrasse 28/30, 48149, Münster (Germany)

[j] Teresa Gatti
Department of Applied Science and Technology
Politecnico di Torino
C.so Duca degli Abruzzi 24, 10129, Torino (Italy)
E-mail: teresa.gatti@polito.it

Table of Contents

Diffusion Measurement	3
Atomic Force Microscopy	8
Photoluminescence Quantum Yield	10
Absorption Coefficients	12
Excitation-Emission Maps and Excitation Spectra	14
Computational Analysis	15
Time-Correlated Single Photon Counting (TCSPC)	16
Degree of Functionalization	17
Photo-Switching	18
Fatigue Resistance	19
Zeta Potential	20
Shake-Flask Method	21
Water Contact Angles	26
NMR Spectra	27
CND.....	27
4-[(1 <i>E</i>)-2-(2,6-Difluorophenyl)diazenyl]-3,5-difluoro-benzoic acid (F-Azo).....	28
CND-F-Azo.....	30
References	31

Diffusion Measurement

For ^1H NMR analyses the samples were dissolved in DMSO- d_6 and sealed in NMR tubes with Parafilm. The respective concentrations of the samples were (i) $10 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ **CND**, (ii) $1 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ ***m*-Azo**, (iii) $10 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ of **CND** and $1 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ of ***m*-Azo** for a physical mixture, and (iv) $11 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ for the **CND-F-Azo**.^[1]

The diffusion measurements were carried out using the stimulated echo experiment with a variation of the gradient pulse strength g . The gradient pulse duration δ was 1 ms and the observation time $\Delta=20$ ms. The resulting echo decays were evaluated by the Stejskal-Tanner equation^[2]:

$$\frac{I}{I_0} = \exp\left(-\gamma^2 \delta^2 g^2 \left(\Delta - \frac{\delta}{3}\right) \cdot D\right) \quad (\text{S1})$$

in which γ denotes the gyromagnetic ratio of the ^1H nucleus and D the molecular diffusion coefficient.

Due to the polydispersity of the CNDs, a single self-diffusion coefficient cannot describe the echo decay sufficiently. To perform an analysis of the echo decays we therefore followed a method described by Lenocho et al.^[3], considering a distribution of diffusion coefficients $P(D)$ with a resulting echo decay of the form:

$$\frac{I}{I_0} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} P^*(D) \exp\left(-\gamma^2 \delta^2 g^2 \left(\Delta - \frac{\delta}{3}\right) \cdot D\right) d\ln(D) \quad (\text{S2})$$

Here, $P^*(D)$ is a modified distribution with $P^*(D) = D \cdot P(D)$. A commonly used function for $P(D)$ in the case of polymer diffusion^[2], but also applicable here, is the log-normal distribution:

$$P(D) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_D D} \exp\left(-\frac{[\ln D - \ln\langle D \rangle]^2}{2\sigma_D^2}\right) \quad (\text{S3})$$

In combination with Equation (S2), $\langle D \rangle$ corresponds to the value at the maximum of the distribution. Using the Stokes-Einstein Equation (S4) the diameter d of the respective diffusing

species was estimated from $\langle D \rangle$. The temperature T during the measurement was 298.4 K, and a value of 2.195 mPa·s was used for the viscosity η of DMSO-d₆^[4] at 298 K.

$$d = \frac{k_B T}{3\pi\eta\langle D \rangle} \quad (\text{S4})$$

Figure S1. 2D DOSY NMR spectra of *m*-Azo measured in DMSO-d₆. Reproduced from Debes et al., *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2025**, with permission from the Royal Society of Chemistry.^[1]

Figure S2. 2D DOSY NMR spectra of **CND** measured in DMSO-d₆. Reproduced from Debes et al., *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2025**, with permission from the Royal Society of Chemistry.^[1]

Figure S3. 2D DOSY NMR spectra of a physical mixture of **CND** (10 mg) and ***m*-Azo** (1 mg) measured in DMSO- d_6 . Reproduced from Debes et al., *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2025**, with permission from the Royal Society of Chemistry.^[1]

Figure S4. 2D DOSY NMR spectra of **CND-F-Azo** CNDs measured in DMSO-d₆.

Atomic Force Microscopy

A $0.02 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ dispersion of the **CND-F-Azo** hybrid in DMSO was drop casted on freshly cleaved V1 grade Mica discs (10 mm diameter, 0.15–0.21 mm thickness). After keeping the prepared samples overnight under reduced pressure, they were measured in AFM tapping mode with a SSS-FMR probe (75 kHz, $2.8 \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$). The obtained images were analyzed with Gwyddion 2.62^[5] and the size of ~ 70 nanoparticles was measured for a size histogram.

Figure S5. $1 \mu\text{m} \times 1 \mu\text{m}$ AFM images of **CND-F-Azo** on a mica substrate. The inset shows the height distribution, with the mean height obtained from ~ 70 CNDs. Size with standard deviation: $2.2 \pm 0.2 \text{ nm}$

Figure S6. (A) 2D AFM image (500×500 nm) of CND-F-Azo. (B) Height profile along the white line in the 2D image. (C) 3D AFM image (500×500 nm) of CND-F-Azo.

Photoluminescence Quantum Yield

The relative PL quantum yield method with quinine sulfate (QS) in 0.1 M H₂SO₄ as a reference compound was used.^[6] For five different concentrations of **CND-F-Azo** the UV-Vis absorbance and PL were measured in DMSO. The maximum values of each absorbance measurement with the respective integrated PL intensity are plotted against each other. From the obtained slope, the already reported reference compound, and the following equation one can calculate the PL quantum yield.

$$\Phi_S = \frac{m_S}{m_R} \cdot \frac{n_S^2}{n_R^2} \cdot \Phi_R \cdot 100$$

Φ_S = quantum yield of the sample [%]

Φ_R = quantum yield of the reference compound (QS = 0.51)

m_S = slope from plotted absorbance against integrated intensity of the sample

m_R = slope from QS^[1] = 1.9 · 10⁶

n_S = 1.4785 refractive index of sample solvent (DMSO)

n_R = 1.33415 refractive index of reference solvent (0.1 M H₂SO₄)

Figure S7. (A) UV-Vis absorbance (solid lines) and PL intensity (dashed lines, $\lambda_{\text{Exc}} = 340$ nm) of

five different concentrated **CND-F-Azo** dispersions. **(B)** Absorbance maxima plotted against the integrated PL intensity of the five different concentrations and the slope derived from a linear fit.

Absorption Coefficients

The UV-Vis absorbance of the **F-Azo** and **CND-F-Azo** samples was measured at five different concentrations in DMSO at 25 °C. The maximum values of each absorbance measurement for the respective concentration were plotted against the concentration. From the obtained slopes and the Law of Lambert-Beer in the following equation, it is possible to determine the absorption coefficient directly.^[7]

$$A = \varepsilon_{\lambda} \cdot c \cdot l$$

A = absorbance [a.u]

ε_{λ} = absorption coefficient at the respective wavelength [$\text{L} \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$]

c = concentration [$\text{mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$]

l = layer thickness of the irradiated body (1 cm)

Figure S8. (A) UV-Vis absorbance of five different concentrated **F-Azo** solutions ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 303$ nm). (B) Absorbance maxima of each concentration plotted against the concentrations, and the respective slopes (absorption coefficients) derived from a linear fit. (C) UV-Vis absorbance of five different concentrated **CND-F-Azo** solutions ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 338$ nm). (D) Absorbance maxima of each concentration plotted against the concentrations, and the respective slopes (absorption coefficients) derived from a linear fit.

Excitation-Emission Maps and Excitation Spectra

Figure S9. (A) Excitation-emission map of **CND-F-Azo** recorded in an excitation wavelength range of 280 nm to 660 nm and an emission wavelength range of 290 nm to 670 nm. Concentration of $6 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ in DMSO was used. (B) Excitation spectra of **CND-F-Azo** recorded at an emission wavelength of 440 nm in the excitation wavelength range of 260 nm to 700 nm. Concentration of $6 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ in DMSO was used. (The signal at 440 nm corresponds to the excitation wavelength, which was not effectively subtracted from the background).

Computational Analysis

Figure S10. Computed long wavelength absorption transitions of the **CND** and **F-Azo** moieties.

Time-Correlated Single Photon Counting (TCSPC)

Fluorescence lifetime measurements were carried out using a custom-built time-correlated single-photon counting (TCSPC) setup. The excitation source was a tunable optical parametric amplifier (Orpheus-HP, Light Conversion), pumped by a 2 MHz carbide laser (CB3-40 W, Light Conversion). The resulting beam was tightly focused into the sample cuvette using a 75 mm focal length lens. Fluorescence emission was collected at 90° relative to the excitation path using a second 75 mm lens. To isolate the emission signal, the fluorescence was passed through a bandpass filter before being focused onto a hybrid photon detector (PMA Hybrid 07, PicoQuant). The detector and the laser's trigger output were connected to a time-tagging module (PicoHarp 330, PicoQuant) for TCSPC data acquisition. All samples were adjusted to an optical density below 0.1 in DMSO to minimize reabsorption effects. Excitation was performed at 340 nm. The resulting fluorescence decay curves (see **Figure 4**) were analyzed using a tail-fit model in the commercial software Fluofit (PicoQuant).

Determination of Transfer Rates and Emission Quenching Efficiencies

The photoluminescence quantum yields Φ were used to calculate the total emission quenching efficiencies $E_Q(\Phi)$ according to following formula,

$$E_Q(\Phi) = 1 - \frac{\Phi_{\text{AzoCND}}}{\Phi_{\text{CND}}}$$

where Φ_{AzoCND} and Φ_{CND} are the average fluorescence lifetimes of the hybrid systems and pure CND, respectively.

Degree of Functionalization

For the quantitative ^{19}F -NMR 10.04 mg of the **CND-F-Azo** were dispersed in 0.75174 g of deuterated DMSO and 0.6 mg of 4,4'-difluorobenzophenone were added to the mixture as an internal standard (IS).^[8] IS: 4,4'-difluorobenzophenone (^{19}F -NMR: $\delta = -106.5$ ppm in DMSO-d₆)

$$b_{\text{amine}} = \frac{\text{Integral}_{\text{CND}}}{\text{Integral}_{\text{IS}}} \cdot \frac{2 \cdot n_{\text{IS}}}{m_{\text{CND}}}$$

$$b_{\text{amine}} = \text{molality} [\text{mol} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}]$$

$$n_{\text{IS}} = \text{amount of internal standard} [\text{mol}]$$

$$m_{\text{CND}} = \text{mass of the CND-F-Azo} [\text{g}]$$

Figure S11. Quantitative ^{19}F -NMR of the **CND-F-Azo** with 4,4'-difluorobenzophenone (IS) measured in DMSO-d₆.

Photo-Switching

The 448 nm LED from Lumitronix or Nichia (LXML-PR01-0500) purchased from leds.de, has a LED output power of 520 mW. The 530 nm LED from Thorlabs (M530L4) has a LED output power of 480 mW.

Figure S12. Absorption spectra of the (A) CND-F-Azo and (B) F-Azo were measured before and after light irradiation. The initial state (black) was measured prior to illumination. The first illumination was conducted with a 530 nm LED for a duration of five minutes (red). The second illumination was conducted with a 448 nm LED for a duration of five minutes (blue). The measurements were performed with an 8 mg L^{-1} dispersion of the hybrid in DMSO at $25 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The measurements were performed with a $5 \text{ } \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ solution of the azo in DMSO at $25 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fatigue Resistance

Figure S13. Absorbance spectra of the **CND-F-Azo** before and after several cycles of light irradiation. One cycle consisted of five minutes of illumination with a 530 nm LED and five minutes of illumination with a 448 nm LED. The measurement was performed with an 8 mg L⁻¹ dispersion in DMSO at 25 °C.

Zeta Potential

Zeta potential measurements at different pH values with an 1 mg L^{-1} **CND-F-Azo** hybrid dispersion in DMSO were performed. The pH value was changed by dropping slowly 0.1 M aqueous HCl into the dispersion. The zeta potential measurements were conducted with a Malvern Zetasizer Nano-ZS device (Malvern, U.K.) at $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The system was operated by the Zetasizer software from Malvern Panlytical (Malvern, U.K.).

Figure S14. Zeta potential measurements of **CND-F-Azo** in DMSO at (A) pH 6 and (B) at pH 7.6. The mean values obtained from three individual measurements are shown in the respective figure.

Shake-Flask Method

The shake-flask test was performed to evaluate the partitioning behavior of the materials. For each experiment, 5 mL of DI water was overlaid with 5 mL of 1-octanol in a glass vial with a snap cap. Then, 2.0 mg of **CND**, 2.1 mg of **F-Azo**, or 2.1 mg of **CND-F-Azo** were added to the biphasic system. The mixtures were stirred overnight at RT using a magnetic stir bar and a stirring plate to allow equilibration between the two phases. After equilibration, the samples were left undisturbed for eight hours to ensure complete phase separation. Then, 225 μL of the mixture was collected from both the octanol and aqueous phases. Each aliquot was diluted with 2.775 mL of spectroscopy-grade DMSO to a final volume of 3 mL for UV-Vis spectroscopic analysis.

A dilution series was created for each sample in its respective phase to obtain the corresponding calibration curve. Since octanol absorbs water up to a molar fraction of 20.7% at RT, the resulting solvent environment in the octanol-rich phase during UV-Vis measurements was approximated by preparing a DMSO-based dilution series that mimics the respective phase.^[8] Based on the reported octanol-water molar fraction of $x = 0.793$ at room temperature (corresponding to an octanol volume fraction of approximately 87.4%), the dilution series for each material in the octanol phase was prepared by adding 225 μL of a solvent mixture containing 197 μL of octanol and 28 μL of water to the respective dilution. This approach ensured that potential solvent effects were minimized during UV-Vis measurements. Conversely, the aqueous phase was considered free of octanol due to the negligible solubility under ambient conditions. Thus, the DMSO-based dilution series for the aqueous phase was prepared by adding 225 μL of pure water to the respective dilution. The corresponding concentration in the octanol phase c_{Octanol} and the water phase c_{Water} of the respective substance was obtained using the calibration functions obtained. Equation S5 was then used to calculate the lipophilicity $\log P$.

$$\log P = \log \left(\frac{c_{\text{Octanol}}}{c_{\text{Water}}} \right) \quad (\text{S5})$$

Figure S15. Calibration curves for the quantification of **CND** in the two-phase shake-flask system.

(A) UV-Vis absorption spectra of **CND** in the octanol phase measured at varying concentrations to construct a calibration curve. (B) Corresponding linear fit for the octanol phase data, yielding the calibration function $y = 0.00823x + 0.00039$. (C) UV-Vis absorption spectra of **CND** in the

aqueous phase measured at varying concentrations. **(D)** Corresponding linear fit for the aqueous phase data, yielding the calibration function $y = 0.00807x + 0.00280$.

Figure S16. Calibration curves for the quantification of **F-Azo** in the two-phase shake-flask system. **(A)** UV-Vis absorption spectra of **F-Azo** in the octanol phase measured at varying concentrations to construct a calibration curve. **(B)** Corresponding linear fit for the octanol phase data, yielding the calibration function $y = 0.01353x - 0.04317$. **(C)** UV-Vis absorption spectra of

F-Azo in the aqueous phase measured at varying concentrations. **(D)** Corresponding linear fit for the aqueous phase data, yielding the calibration function $y = 0.01323x - 0.05027$.

Figure S17. Calibration curves for the quantification of **CND-F-Azo** in the two-phase shake-flask system. **(A)** UV-Vis absorption spectra of **CND-F-Azo** in the octanol phase measured at varying concentrations to construct a calibration curve. **(B)** Corresponding linear fit for the octanol phase data, yielding the calibration function $y = 0.007975x - 0.001515$. **(C)** UV-Vis absorption spectra

of **CND-F-Azo** in the aqueous phase measured at varying concentrations. **(D)** Corresponding linear fit for the aqueous phase data, yielding the calibration function $y = 0.008183x + 0.0007$.

A – CND

B – F-Azo

C – CND-F-Azo

Figure S18. Pictures of the two-phase mixture after it was stirred overnight and equilibrated. **(A)** CND, **(B)** F-Azo, and **(C)** CND-F-Azo, which shows aggregate formation.

Water Contact Angles

We examined the polarity of the surfaces by measuring their water contact angles θ . Glass microscope slides were cleaned with EtOH, acetone, and a UV-ozone cleaner. The slides were then spin-coated twice with **CND** or **CND-F-Azo**, using 200 μL of an 8 mg mL^{-1} EtOH:H₂O (1:1) dispersion. The slides were spin-coated at 20 rps for two minutes. The coated substrates were dried overnight under reduced pressure. The initial water contact angle for the uncoated glass substrate was 9.2°. The **CND**-coated glass showed a reduced water contact angle of 5.6°, reflecting an increase in surface polarity due to immobilization of the **CND**. As expected, the **CND-F-Azo** showed an increased water contact angle of 14.2°, consistent with reduced polarity. The water contact angle values presented herein are the mean values of six distinct positions of the respective sample.

Figure S19. (A) Pure glass surface: contact angle $\theta = 9.2^\circ$, (B) Glass surface coated with **CND**: contact angle $\theta = 5.6^\circ$, (C) Glass surface coated with **CND-F-Azo**: contact angle $\theta = 14.2^\circ$

NMR Spectra

CND

Figure S20. ¹H-NMR spectra of CND measured in DMSO-d₆.

4-[(1E)-2-(2,6-Difluorophenyl)diazenyl]-3,5-difluoro-benzoic acid (F-Azo)

Figure S21. ¹H-NMR spectra of 4-[(1E)-2-(2,6-Difluorophenyl)diazenyl]-3,5-difluoro-benzoic acid (F-Azo) measured in CDCl₃.

Figure S22. ^{19}F -NMR spectra of 4-[(1*E*)-2-(2,6-Difluorophenyl)diazenyl]-3,5-difluoro-benzoic acid (**F-Azo**) measured in CDCl_3 .

CND-F-Azo

Figure S23. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra of the **CND-F-Azo** hybrid measured in DMSO-d_6 .

References

- [1] P. P. Debes, D. Schatz, Y. Aydogan-Sun, J. P. Martínez, M. Langer, J. Hessling, J. Gallego, E. Menna, B. M. Smarsly, M. Schönhoff, S. Osella, J. Wachtveitl, H. A. Wegner, T. Gatti, *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2025**, *13*, 11879–11889.
- [2] W. S. Price, *NMR Studies of Translational Motion: Principles and Applications*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, **2009**.
- [3] A. Lench, M. Schumacher, A. H. Gröschel, C. Cramer, M. Schönhoff, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* **2023**, *224*, 2300286.
- [4] A. Sacco, E. Matteoli, *J. Solut. Chem.* **1997**, *26*, 527–535.
- [5] D. Nečas, P. Klapetek, **2012**.
- [6] M. Levitus, *Methods Appl. Fluoresc.* **2020**, *8*, 033001.
- [7] R. Luther, A. Nikolopoulos, *Z. Für Phys. Chem.* **1913**, *82U*, 361–384.
- [8] E. Voutsas, in *Thermodyn. Solubility Environ. Issues* (Ed.: T.M. Letcher), Elsevier, Amsterdam, **2007**, pp. 205–227.